

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF AZERBAIJANI COMMUNITY IN AZERBAIJANI-DAGESTANI RELATIONS

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Abstract

The Azerbaijani community has a long-standing history in the modern territory of Dagestan. Throughout the centuries, the Azerbaijani language has served as a lingua franca for the various peoples of Dagestan. During the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Azerbaijanis established numerous educational and charitable organizations, which played a pivotal role in shaping the political consciousness of the local population. The Azerbaijani community in Dagestan plays a significant role in the social and economic development of the region. Their contribution is essential in building good neighborly relationships with Azerbaijan. This article examines the various aspects of the Azerbaijani community's participation in developing comprehensive relations between Dagestan and Azerbaijan. The study involved analyzing archival documents, media materials, reports, and official documentation of the governments of both Azerbaijan and Dagestan. The descriptive-comparative method was applied in analyzing historical documents.

Keywords: Dagestani-Azerbaijani cooperation, Azerbaijani community, economic relations, historical relations, educational societies.

Introduction. The collapse of the USSR and the subsequent declaration of independence of its former republics had systemic consequences that changed the geopolitical, geo-cultural, and ethno-cultural image of the entire space of the former USSR. Nations that once lived in a single economic, political, and sociocultural space found themselves on opposite sides of new borders. This resulted in a noticeable deterioration of inter-ethnic relations, making it one of the most vulnerable issues in the mosaic sociocultural space. Given the current conditions, it is vital to reconstruct the centuries-old, diverse relationships between neighboring peoples who share common historical destinies. This issue has a direct impact on the modern geopolitical processes that are unfolding in the Caucasus, and it is also crucial for developing a well-thought-out and scientifically balanced concept of state policy to regulate the development of historical established ties with neighboring nations such as the peoples of Dagestan and Azerbaijan.

It is worth noting that the relationship between the peoples of Dagestan and Azerbaijan has been the subject of extensive research by domestic and foreign scholars specializing in Caucasian Studies [22; 10; 9; 12; 13]. During the Soviet period, a focused study of the social, economic, and political relationships between the peoples of the region was initiated. Soviet historiography conducted extensive research that emphasized different facets of the history of the Dagestan nations, including their interactions with the people of Azerbaijan [20; 8; 16; 5]. Scientific research now explores the diverse relationship between Azerbaijan and Dagestan [11; 25; 17].

The relationship between the peoples of Dagestan and Azerbaijan has a long history, dating back centuries, and is influenced by various factors such as trade, economics, politics, and culture. Derbent, a fortress city, holds a significant role in the ethnocultural ties between the two regions. It has been an important center

for economic, political, and cultural relations between Azerbaijan and Dagestan since ancient times and played a crucial role in the social and cultural life of the entire Caucasus region. The Azerbaijani community was the largest group in this city and played a significant role in the social and political life of the region. At the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th century, when the interests of Great Powers conflicted in the North-Eastern Caucasus, the peoples of Dagestan and Azerbaijan worked together to find the best solution for their future. Following the formation of the Soviet Union, the peoples of Azerbaijan and Dagestan became a part of a single state, which strengthened their political and cultural ties. After the collapse of the USSR, the Dagestani and Azerbaijani people faced significant consequences. Prior to 1991, the area they inhabited was never separated by a state border since the time Azerbaijan was incorporated into the Russian Empire. Since then, both the people and the states occupying the land have undergone significant transformation processes.

Azerbaijani community and Azerbaijani-Dagestani relations in the modern era

The earliest records of the Turkic people in modern Dagestan date back to the early Middle Ages. [3, p.7-13]. Azerbaijanis from Dagestan have settled in the coastal and foothill regions of Southern Dagestan, particularly in the city of Derbent and its surrounding areas. The Terekeme people played a significant role in the formation of Azerbaijanis in Dagestan through assimilation processes. These people settled in Temiraul, Chontaul, and partly in Kostek and Aksai villages. By the end of the 19th century, they became part of the Kumyk ethnic group. Towards the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th centuries, there were extensive processes of Turkization of Tato-speaking, Arabic-speaking, and Tabasaran villages. During the early 20th century, the Tat language was gradually replaced by

Azerbaijani due to the increasing interethnic communication and the teaching of Azerbaijani as a native language at schools [24, p.16-17]. Azerbaijani scholars, such as Shirvanly Khasmagomed, Abdulla Agdashli and many others, taught in mollakhans, madrasahs, and other educational institutions in Dagestan [24, p.17]. Various Azerbaijani educational and charitable societies and wealthy individuals opened schools teaching in Azerbaijani and national printing houses and distributed Azerbaijani newspapers about life in the Caucasus among the population in the Dagestan region. [14, p. 168]. During the imperial period, Russian-Azerbaijani schools of the Baku-Dagestan Directorate of Public Schools functioned in Dagestan [1, f.309, op.2, d 749, p.67]. Today, about 117 thousand Azerbaijanis live in the Republic of Dagestan, which is 3.7% of the population of the republic [6].

Azerbaijan is a diverse country with several large Caucasian-speaking communities. The northern part of the country is home to the Nakh-Dagestan family of peoples, which includes the Lezgins, Avars, and Tsakhurs. According to the latest census, the Lezgins are the second largest ethnic group in Azerbaijan [2, p.333-334]. Azerbaijani community of Dagestan and Lezgin community of Azerbaijan consider Azerbaijan and Dagestan as their shared homeland. These communities have a significant impact on the political relations between Dagestan and Azerbaijan.

The Azerbaijani community in Dagestan plays a crucial role in the socio-political life of the republic and in strengthening the relationship between Azerbaijan and Dagestan. This community has a positive influence on the resolution of political issues such as interethnic relations, border delimitation, and the fight against religious extremism. National leader of Azerbaijan Heydar Aliyev played a vital role in developing ties between the peoples of Azerbaijan and Dagestan. His efforts led to the resolution of many issues related to national representation in government agencies, interethnic problems, and the establishment of mutual trust.

Azerbaijanis who occupy important government positions in Dagestan contribute to the development of political ties between the two republics. Said Kurbanov, who successfully led the Derbent region for a long time, modernized the relationship of the Azerbaijani community with the political authorities of Azerbaijan in various fields of activity. An influential politician, general director of the Radioelement plant, deputy of the Derbent city assembly, Ragimov Seyran is a key figure in the development of Azerbaijani-Dagestan relations. He was the chairman of the Dagestan regional branch of the All-Russian Azerbaijani Congress and the President of the public organization "Derbent-Azeri". Mutual visits by the political leadership of Azerbaijan and Dagestan indicate their political ties. The political leaders of Dagestan often visit Azerbaijan to discuss strategic cooperation [4].

The increase in activity of organized crime, terrorist, and extremist organizations, as well as other destabilizing factors, highlights the need for political cooperation between Azerbaijan and Dagestan. Meetings and consultations between the relevant authorities of both states at the highest level have made it possible to

fight against organized crime and other negative phenomena [15, p.50–65]. Political cooperation among the republics is crucial in the battle against religious extremism. In the years 2007-2008, there was an increase in the number of followers of the Wahhabism ideology, particularly in the northern regions of the republic, where ethnic Dagestanis, such as Avars and Lezgins, reside. The responsible parties for spreading Wahhabism throughout the entire Caucasus region are international Islamist and terrorist organizations. Effective actions and coordination of national security agencies is essential in the fight against these organizations [18, p.220-226]. The political and religious situation in Azerbaijan and Dagestan is being well managed due to the joint efforts of both sides. Recently, there has been an increase in political relations between Azerbaijan and Dagestan through various meetings and discussions held at different levels. Representatives of the Azerbaijani community of Dagestan widely participated in these events. In June 2007, an international scientific and practical conference titled "Historical, cultural and economic ties of the peoples of Dagestan and Azerbaijan: a look at the 21st century from the experience of the past" was held at the Dagestan Scientific Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences in Dagestan. The conference was held to commemorate Aziz Aliyev, an Azerbaijani political figure who was the head of the Dagestan region from 1942 to 1948 and the grandfather of the current President of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev.

The key to maintaining good political relations with neighboring country is through economic cooperation. In 2011, the Russian-Azerbaijani Economic Forum was held in Dagestan's capital for the first time. The forum presented investment opportunities and sites in the Republic of Dagestan to its participants. Azerbaijan and Dagestan are interested in establishing ties in various fields such as industry, trade, transportation, and tourism. A promising area of cooperation between Dagestan and Azerbaijan is in the development of the Caspian Sea shelf adjacent to the region. Dagestan considers it a priority to develop new fields, transport, and refine oil in the Caspian Sea, which will improve the economic situation, increase employment, budget revenues, and resolve socially important issues. In this regard, the most profitable solution would be to establish interaction between Dagestan's oil and gas company and Azerbaijani enterprises. This cooperation would be impossible without active involvement of the representatives of the Azerbaijani community of Dagestan.

For many years, Azerbaijan has been in first place in terms of volume of product exports to the Republic of Dagestan. In 2010, foreign trade transactions worth \$209.7 million were carried out between Azerbaijan and Dagestan [21]. The regional public organization "Gardens of Friendship" and the "Dagestan-Azerbaijan Charitable Society" have been effective in developing economic cooperation. Azerbaijani shipping and the Makhachkala International Sea Trade Port are crucial in establishing and developing regular maritime transport links between Iran and Russia [19, p.131]. In 2019, trade turnover between Azerbaijan and Russia increased to 3 billion, and in 2022 reached 13 billion US dollars [23].

Dagestan is an attractive region for Azerbaijani state and businessmen who are looking to invest. The area is primarily a transit region and a profitable consumer market for Azerbaijan. Railway, highway, and sea routes that pass through Dagestan connect Azerbaijan with various regions of Europe and Russia. Private sector representatives from Azerbaijan are interested in constructing thermal complexes and logistics centers that are important for trading fruits and vegetables in Dagestan. In February 2023, the Deputy Prime Minister of Azerbaijan, Shahin Mustafayev, and the Chairman of the Government of Dagestan, Abdulmuslim Abdulmuslimov, signed an action plan for the development of key areas of cooperation between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Dagestan for 2023-2025. The document aims to establish industrial cooperation and intensify investment attraction.

Cultural and educational ties play a significant role in strengthening good neighborly relations and mutual understanding between different countries and their people. Azerbaijan and Dagestan established broad cultural ties back in the Soviet era, when Azerbaijani artistic groups frequently toured Dagestan [7]. Azerbaijani literature has played a crucial role in introducing the people of Dagestan to the works of Russian and European classics. Today, the cultural exchange between the two peoples has become more organized and focused. The foundation for direct cooperation in the field of science and education between the Republic of Dagestan and the Republic of Azerbaijan was laid at the end of the 20th century. In 1993, the Derbent branch of the Azerbaijan State Economic University was established on the initiative of national leader Heydar Aliyev, with the aim of providing higher education for Azerbaijani community of Derbent. Citizens of Azerbaijan living in the border zone, especially in the Khachmaz and Gusar regions, study at universities located in the territory of the Republic of Dagestan.

Scientific collaboration between Azerbaijan and Dagestan is happening in multiple areas. Firstly, scientists from both countries participate in scientific conferences, seminars and symposiums that address various issues in the field of science. For several years, there has been a seminar called "Magnetic Phase Transitions" for young physicists held in Makhachkala. In April 2010, an international conference titled "Azerbaijan-Dagestan: History of Fraternal Relations, Modernity, Prospects" took place in Baku. In 2019, the first international scientific and practical conference on "Advocacy within the Framework of Caspian Cooperation" was held in Dagestan, with members of the Bar Association representing Azerbaijan.

The Days of Dagestan is an event that has been held regularly since 2016 to further develop the cultural ties between Azerbaijan and Dagestan. The event takes place in several cities of Azerbaijan, including Khachmaz, Balaken, Gusar and Zagatala. During the event, cultural figures from Dagestan perform concerts and shows. The Azerbaijani community of Dagestan actively participates in the activities of the regional society "Promoting the Development of Friendship, Cultural, Economic and Social Ties between Dagestan and Azerbaijan", which was created in 2019. The society

aims to enhance the existing relations between the two republics and expand areas of cooperation.

Conclusion. The strength of the relationship between Azerbaijan and Dagestan is determined by the statements and positions of the political leaders of both states. The stability, development, and depth of these relations depend on the foreign policy of Russia and Azerbaijan, which plays a crucial role in ensuring security in the region. A study has shown that maintaining friendly relations, political will, mutual trust, inclusiveness in domestic policies, as well as economic and cultural cooperation between local communities, leads to economic growth and political stability. These factors also help to eliminate controversial issues and inter-ethnic tensions. Therefore, it is important to maintain these relationships in various ways.

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